

ISic3688

I.Sicily inscription 3688

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

local stone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2015.12.28

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Vittoria

Provenance

Found in late 1970s or early 1980s during work on sewage plant by the Ippari river, below Vittoria (36.929038, 14.531914)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Vittoria, Polimuseo Attilio
Zarino

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:****Bibliography**

Lavore, V. 1983. L'epigrafe di Charinos: lettura e prospettive di studio. Vittoria.

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